

Aziz Umarov Olimovich
Chief Adviser of the Department of Justice

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5949341>

SOME ISSUES OF COMPLEX SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL STUDY OF CONTRACTUAL RELATIONS OF AIRCRAFT LEASING

Annotation: *Today, our scientists have studied lease agreements in detail and revealed many aspects. However, the issues of the aircraft lease agreement and its contractual relationship have not been studied by scientists. An important task is to conduct a comprehensive, scientific and theoretical study of the contractual relationship of aircraft leasing, as well as to make proposals on the issues studied.*

Keywords: *Leasing agreement, aircraft, contractual relations*

Today, new Uzbekistan is a unique path of development, a new worldview, new reforms that glorify human dignity. Consistently high growth rates in all spheres, stable and reliable functioning of the banking and financial system, modernization and changes in the economy, in general, our bold steps to increase the investment attractiveness of our country to the world community, as well as the International Monetary Fund, World Bank, Asian Development is recognized by reputable international financial institutions such as the Bank.

It is no secret that our country has a strong transport system. The initiative of President Sh. Mirziyoyev to establish a Regional Center for the Development of Transport and Communications under the auspices of the United Nations is seen as an important factor in the development of transport and communications in the region. On January 28, 1992, the national airline "Uzbekistan Airways" was established. During the years of independence, the National Airline has not only demonstrated its competitiveness in the international transport market, but also gained the trust of customers and significantly expanded the scope of its activities. Renewal of the fleet with modern aircraft such as Boeing -757/767, A-320, A-310 will play an important role in the development of the industry. The Airbus A-320 aircraft purchased under the lease agreement has been successfully operating international and domestic routes. The purchase of new V-767 aircraft included in the order portfolio of our national airline, as well as the replenishment of the fleet of our national airline with new aircraft is one of the main conditions for the development of the industry. The high cost of aircraft does not allow to buy it directly, on the basis of a contract of sale. In turn, the question arises: then how to buy aircraft? We believe that the most optimal solution to the problem is to purchase the aircraft in accordance with the lease agreement and then pay for it in installments. This requires a thorough study of the leasing relationship, especially the legal basis of the aircraft lease agreement, scientific research.

A lot of scientific work has been done in our country and abroad on certain aspects of leasing agreements. Uzbek scientists K. Rashidov, O. Hazratkulov, M. Baratov, S.

Boboqulov, T. Kocher-gina, Sh. Yuldasheva conducted research on issues such as leasing agreements, international leasing agreements, international legal regulation of leasing relations.

Scientists from the Commonwealth of Independent States M. Braginsky, V. Vitryanskiy, V. In the scientific works of Gazman, A.Ivanov, E.Kabatova, A.Smirnov, Yu.Kharitonov and others, issues such as leasing relations, its legal nature, certain aspects of the lease agreement, such as financial leasing, insurance of leasing activities, collateral in the lease agreement are reflected.

The above scientific works reveal many aspects of the lease agreement, scientifically, thoroughly studied. However, the issues of the aircraft lease agreement, its contractual relationship have not been studied by scientists. The main goal is to conduct a comprehensive, scientific and theoretical study of the contractual relationship of aircraft leasing, as well as to make proposals on the studied issues.

REVIEWS:

1. Рашидов К.К. Значение общепризнанных норм международного права и развития гражданского законодательства. // Материалы международной научно-практической конференции "Гражданское право Республики Узбекистан за десять лет ее независимости". -Т.: ТГЮИ, 2001.-С.175-179.
2. Ҳазратқулов Ў.Т. Лизинг муносабатларининг халқаро ҳуқуқий тартибга солиниши. // "Гармонизация законодательства Республики Узбекистан и Европейская Союз" "Илмий – амалий конф. Маъруза матн. -Т.:2004.-Б.84-89.
3. Баратов М. Яна лизинг ҳақида (хамм.)//Ҳуқуқий маърифат Ахборотномаси. -1999.-8-сон.
4. Бобоқулов С. Договор о лизинге. //Хўжалик ва ҳуқуқ.-2002. 8-сон.
5. Кочергина Т. Правовой режим лизинговых обязательств.//Фуқаролик қонунчилиги.илмий конференция материаллари.-Т.: ТДЮИ,2004.-82б.
6. Юлдашева Ш.Лизинг шартномаси. //Ёш олимлар тўплами.-2004.-6-сон.-Б. 22-24.
7. Брагинский М.И., Витрянский В.В. Договорное право. Книга первая и вторая: Общие положения. М.: Статут, 2000.
8. Витрянский В.В. Договор аренды и его виды: прокат, фрахтование на время, аренда зданий, сооружений и предприятий, лизинг. Изд. 3-е М.: Статут, 2001.
9. Газман В.Д. Лизинг: Теория, практика, комментарии. М., 1997.
10. Иванов А.А. Договор финансовой аренды (лизинга): Учебно-практическое пособие. М.: Проспект, 2001.
11. Кабатова Е.В. Лизинг: правовое регулирование, практика. М.: ИН-ФРА-М, 1997.
12. Смирнов А.Л. Лизинговые операции / Серия «Международный банковский бизнес». М.: Издательство АО «Консалтбанкир», 1995.

13. Харитонова Ю.С. Договор лизинга. М.: Юрайт-М, 2002.